

Quantum Mechanics and Time versus Space Sampling of Spatial Distributions

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Classical mechanics samples space as being uniform i.e. each x point having the same weight. Thus the number of x states in a length L is proportional to L or in 3-space to volume V . The \ln of this value then appears in classical entropy calculations. In the case of a particle moving in space the same idea holds, but this means the particle spends equal amounts of time in each dx region. Thus we argue this result of a constant probability in space is based on time sampling. Time sampling is the sampling done for an equilibrium gas. The system does not change on average in time, so it is as if one has a snapshot. Thus one has a constant probability in a length L in time sampling. One may argue that this constant is information so $\ln(\text{probability}(x)) = \text{constant}1$ or $P(x) = \text{constant} 2$.

The relativistic/nonrelativistic action may be written as $A = -Et + px$ if one uses $v = x/t$. This Lorentz invariant form allows one to clearly separate t and x with E and p as constants and may also be considered to be information. In such a case, if one ignores time, then px is the spatial contribution to A and this does represent a constant probability in space. Rather there is scaling of space by p . If $x = \text{constant}/p$, then each p has its own unique length, called a wavelength, in which space sampling is the same i.e. creates the same distribution form, but with $1/p$ as the wavelength. This we argue is space sampling of a spatial distribution and has physical consequences (i.e. two slit interference, measuring small regions etc). One may note that the wavelength $= \hbar/p$ depends on the magnitude of p . In actuality, p has a direction as this is space sampling. If px is considered to be information, then $\ln(\text{probability}(x)) = px$ or probability $x = \exp(ipx)$. To obtain time sampling, one needs to freeze out motion i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ (AND situation).

Thus the manner in which one samples an underlying distribution may give rise to a different distribution. Arguing that a particle spends the same amount of time in each dx region and so the spatial probability is constant completely ignores the form px from the classical action.

$\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a wavelength, thus x samples are within different lengths for different p 's. This suggests an associated entropy which is not additive because one loses information when adding $p_1 + p_2$. Probability $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1 + p_2)x)$, however, is conserved as is the overall impulse $p_1 + p_2$ which depends only on the net momentum, whereas p_1 entropy depends on a specific value.

Different Probability Distributions Depending on the Data Sampled

As we have argued before (1), a given system may yield different probability distributions and hence different entropies based on the information measured. For example, a die has probabilities of $1/6$ and a corresponding Shannon's entropy $\ln(6)$ if one measures the 6 possible outcomes. If, however, one only measures even or odd numbers, the probability is $1/2$ even and $1/2$ odd and a different Shannon's entropy results i.e. $\ln(2)$. Similarly for a single particle quantum bound state, if one knocks out the single particle and measures its p (momentum) one has a probability $a(p)a(p)$ together with a uniform spatial distribution. On the other, spatial

measurements yield $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ which combines momentum and spatial information and yields a different entropy.

Thus we argue that one's choice of information in a system (which one measures) governs the probability distribution one sees.

Time Sampling of a Spatial Distribution

By time sampling of a spatial distribution we mean one considers average spatial positions as time passes. This is the approach used in the classical statistical mechanics of a gas. At equilibrium, the system does not change in time so time sampling is like sampling from a static system i.e. one in which motion has been frozen. For a particle moving at a constant p (any p , any velocity and any direction in one dimension), a frozen momentum picture yields equidistributed particles spatially as no x carries extra weight. Time sampling leads to a constant x probability distribution.

On the other hand, if one considers information to be a constant b (because all x values have the same weight, then:

$$\ln(\text{probability}) = b \text{ or } \text{probability} = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

Spatial Sampling of a Spatial Distribution

We argue that there is a different way to sample a spatial distribution even in the classical scenario. This is equivalent to choosing a different information. Given that one considers space, one must consider both directions whereas the time sampling treats these two as equivalent in terms of the distribution. In fact, motion is frozen in time sampling. We argue that spatial sampling not only brings in the direction, but the value of momentum. Thus it must be based on a different information in the system. We choose this information as the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2)) \text{ by ignoring } -Et \text{ because we are only interested in spatial features.}$$

$$\text{Then: } \ln(\text{probability}) = px \text{ or } \text{probability} = \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

An "i" is used so that probability is periodic rather than growing or shrinking indefinitely. ((3)) distinguishes direction. One may note that ((2)) as a Lorentz invariant should represent information. It is also the relativistic/nonrelativistic action if one writes: $v=x/t$.

Two different information forms yield two different probability distributions. It is argued that time sampling is equivalent to freezing out information. If this is the case, then freezing motion should be equivalent to:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \text{Probability}(p) \text{ AND } \text{Probability}(-p) = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

Thus the x sampling result is linked to the time sampling one

We note that in $p x$, p scales x . The result $\exp(ipx)$ shows this same property in that $\text{constant}/p$ represents a wavelength. In other words, for different p values, the same number of sample points occur, but in a different length scale i.e. \hbar/p . For a given p , if one has n sample points, then:

Product over i $\exp(i p x_i)$ is a constant over a wavelength ((5))

This occurs because the $x_0=0$ for any p and scale a $1/p$. ((5)) is the same for all p values.

It is interesting to note that in classical physics one considers time sampling and so a given x length is proportional to the number of sampling points regardless of p or v . In the quantum (x sampling from the Lorentz invariant approach) this is not the case. A high p has a small wavelength \hbar/p , but the same number of sampling points are found within each wavelength. For a fixed x , there are more sampling points for a high p i.e. a high p yields more data about the region x . As we have argued in previous notes, one may try to capture this extra information for high p values by considering $C |\cos(px)|$ as the probability within a length L . Then a high p has more max peaks compared to a low p and this is like comparing a die to a coin and leads to different entropies at this level.

Lorentz Information and Additivity

If one chooses $p x$ as the x sampling information, then $p_1 x + p_2 x = (p_1 + p_2)x$ i.e. information is additive. This is linked with conservation of p (momentum) i.e. one does not gain or lose information. Physically, an impulse by p_1 and p_2 at the same time is equivalent to a single impulse of $p_1 + p_2$. The sampling regions, however, differ. p_1 has a sampling region of \hbar/p_1 and p_2 one of \hbar/p_2 while $p_1 + p_2$ has a sampling region of $\hbar/(p_1 + p_2)$. What is conserved is the probability associated with the information i.e. $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1 + p_2)x)$.

One may consider whether the spatial sampling x entropy is extensive. As a crude estimate, consider 2 peaks within every wavelength \hbar/p . Then for a given L , there are: $2pL/\hbar$ peaks so the probability is: $\hbar/2pL$. If one has p_1 and p_2 adding to yield $p_1 + p_2$, then p_1 has a probability distribution associated with $\hbar/2p_1L$, p_2 with $\hbar/2p_2L$ and $p_1 + p_2$ with $\hbar/2(p_1 + p_2)L$.

Entropy p_1 + Entropy p_2 versus Entropy $(p_1 + p_2)$

$-\ln(\hbar/2p_1L) - \ln(\hbar/2p_2L)$ versus $-\ln(\hbar/2(p_1 + p_2)L)$

Or: $\ln(p_1) + \ln(p_2) \neq \ln(p_1 + p_2)$ in general where p_i is momentum

The entropy of the sampling data for a given p is specific to that p . It is not extensive. Combining p_1 and p_2 keeps the physical effect of impulse the same, but information is lost in the combination of p_1 and p_2 (i.e. given the vector sum $p_1 + p_2$ one does not know what p_1 and

p_2 created it) and so sampling length changes for p_1+p_2 . Physically, however, this loss of information does not change the impulse.

By being able to discern p_1 and p_2 separately (and not just the sum) one is able to sense the information associated with each, but the overall sum may have a different information (in terms of peaks in a given length).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the manner in which one samples data affects the probability distribution one sees, even for the same classical system. We argue that in classical statistical mechanics one uses a time sampling approach i.e. an equilibrium system does not change in time. This is equivalent to a freezing of motion (or a static snapshot). For constant p , or no potential, one expects particles to be equally distributed along a length L . The information is thus a constant, say b , and $\ln(\text{probability}(x))=b$ or $\text{probability}(x)=\text{constant}$.

We argue that the Lorentz information $-Et+px$ (with Et ignored if one is only interested in spatial information) means px is also information (x sampling). Then $\ln(\text{probability}(x)) = ipx$ because one wishes to have periodic, not growing or shrinking probability, so $\text{probability}(x)=\exp(ipx)$ which distinguishes direction. Freezing out motion means: $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \text{constant}$ which yields the time sampling result.

We note that $\exp(ipx)$ implies a kind of entropy linked with a probability of $C |\cos(px)|$ over a length L . This entropy does not seem to be additive as combining p_1 and p_2 to obtain p_1+p_2 results in a loss of information i.e. given the sum p_1+p_2 , one does not know the values of p_1 and p_2 and each of these has their own sampling wavelength. Probability, however, is conserved as $\exp(ip_1 x) \exp(ip_2 x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2) x)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Selective Entropy Based on Measurement, Conjugate Variables and Quantum Numbers (preprint, zenodo, 2023)